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**PREDICTION OF GLASS TRANSITION TEMPERATURE AND
KEY ENGINEERING PROPERTIES OF DRY/WET EPOXY BASED
COMPOSITE MATRIX**

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INTRODUCTION

In polymer composites moisture absorption significantly reduces the performance by plasticizing the matrix, which is often an epoxy resin. Much attention has been given to a study of the effects of moisture on key properties of matrix resins. It was found that absorbed water is located in nanovoids [1] which form the free volume of the material [2] and the total amount of absorbed moisture is not the same as the free volume.

The use of such experimental method as positron annihilation spectroscopy [3-4] allowed to measure the size and the quantity of such sites. Polarity of the network has a strong influence over the moisture uptake resulting in greater moisture content at equilibrium for more polar systems [5]. The moisture transport phenomenon has also been studied in detail where two types of hydrogen links between water and a polymer were found. Type 1 mostly affects the interchain interactions resulting in plasticization and lowering of the T_g whereas the type 2 bridges the segments by secondary crosslinking through hydroxyl groups [6]. The last mechanism is significantly affected by hydrothermal aging [6].

Plasticization of the network is generally believed to be a reversible process [7] and the equilibrium concentration of water mainly depends on type of resin and conditioning [1]. Data on irreversible degradation of matrix and hydrolysis was also reported for some resin systems [8].

Some researchers believe that because water molecule is linked to resin structural groups it may participate in the relaxation process. Assumptions were made from the study of secondary relaxations of polymers [9].

Since the glass transition temperature is moisture content dependent it is appropriate to examine the effect of moisture absorption on the glass transition temperature as a function of moisture content.

Among experimental methods for measuring the glass transition temperature and the effect of moisture absorption, Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) is the most common. It is efficient for the study of a single component resins and multifunctional blends. Another method such as Thermally Stimulated Depolarization

Current technique can be applied for studying the influence of water on segment relaxation in polymers [10]. Theoretical background can be analyzed by Group Interaction Modelling (GIM) a method derived from the basis of lattice model and rotational isomeric state theory.

This paper reports the application of group interaction modelling and related models to the prediction of the broadening of glass-rubber transition for dry state and on moisture absorption. The engineering properties such as yield stress and tensile modulus of the matrix have also been modelled from the GIM principles.

MODELLING

GIM is based on the energy balance which considers inter chain interactions. The GIM concept is based on the solution of the main model potential function (formula 1) this allowed a derivation of a new set of simplified formulas giving the practical estimates of major properties from the polymer molecular structure.

$$\phi = -\phi_0 + H_C + H_T + H_m = \phi_0 \left[\left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right)^{12} - 2 \left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right)^6 \right] \quad (1)$$

where H_C , H_T and H_m are configurational, thermal and mechanical energies respectively, ϕ_0 and r_0 are the potential and separation distance at the state of lowest interaction energy.

The key model input parameters (calculated from the group contribution tables) are the cohesive energy E_{coh} , number of degrees of freedom N and Van der Waals volume, V_w . The cohesive energy sums all interaction forces and is proportional to the potential of the system at the lowest energy. Number of degrees of freedom introduces the ability of a structural segment to rotate and change its conformation and Van der Waals volume defines the unpenetrable volume of the chain groups. For convenience the simplified predictive equations derived from the main balance equation (formula 1) in GIM are written in terms of these model input parameters [11].

Predictions of Glass Transition Temperature and Modelling of DMTA relaxation spectra.

The glass transition temperature is given by formula 2 which can be expanded for predictions on complex thermoset polymers [12].

$$T_g = 0.224 \cdot \theta + 0.0513 \cdot \frac{E_{coh}}{N} \quad (2)$$

$$T_g = 0.224 \cdot \theta + 0.0513 \cdot \frac{E_{coh}_{mon} + x_{stH1} \cdot E_{coh}_{H1} + x_{stH2} \cdot E_{coh}_{H2} - \Delta E_{et} - \omega}{(N_{mon} - f \cdot N_L) + x_{stH1} \cdot N_{H1} + x_{stH2} \cdot N_{H2}} \quad (3)$$

where f is an average functionality of the polymer mer unit, N_L - is number of degrees of freedom lost by each reacted group, ω - is the cohesive energy conversion coefficient, θ is the GIM reference temperature.

The stoichiometric coefficient of hardener in equation 3 can be found from the hardener weight fraction. It represents the amount of hardener per single mer unit and is calculated from the component molecular weights and a hardener weight fraction:

$$x_{st H} = \frac{M_{ep}}{M_H} \cdot w_H \quad (4)$$

where M_{ep} and M_H are relative molecular masses of the epoxy monomer and hardener respectively, and w_H is the weight fraction of hardener.

The expanded formula 2 was used to estimate the glass transition temperature of 924-epoxy resin and its separately cured constituents. 924-epoxy resin (Hexcel Ltd.) a composite matrix with 50:50 blend of tetrafunctional glycidyl amine (MY721) and the triglycidyl aminophenol (MY0510) monomers cured with diaminodiphenylsulphone (DDS) and dicyandiamide (DICY).

The Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis was used for the glass transition temperature measurement and Differential Scanning Calorimetry to determine the degree of cure /Table 1/.

Table 1. Predicted and Experimental Glass Transition Temperatures and the Degree of cure of Investigated Resin Systems.

Resin Type	MY0510-DDS	MY0510-DICY	MY721-DDS	MY721-DICY	924-epoxy
$Tg_{cal}, ^\circ C$	283	213	281	249	241
$Tg_{exp}, ^\circ C$	285	218	288	258	234
Conversion,%	95	82	87	85	92

Table 1 shows that GIM based model is compliant with experimental data.

The full relaxation envelope of DMTA for 924-epoxy can also be modelled by scaling the degrees of cure of base resin components to fit the onset relaxation peak of 924-epoxy /Figure 1/. This was done by applying the Gaussian fit originally used by Rotter and Ishida [13] and defining the center of the curves as a modelled Tg value.

Figure 1. A Schematic Representation of the Contribution of the Component Resins to the Experimental DMTA Relaxation Curve of 924-epoxy Matrix
The effect of moisture absorption on Tg can be predicted by including model parameters of cohesive energy and degrees of freedom of water molecule. This is shown on example of 924-epoxy /Figure 2/.

Figure 2. Comparison of Predicted and Experimental Glass Transition Temperatures for 924-epoxy Resin as a Function of Moisture Uptake.

Similar correlations were plotted to assess the effect of moisture on the component resins. This made possible the simulation of the effect of moisture on the relaxation peaks for the constituents in Figure 1. The concentration of moisture absorbed by base resins within the blend was assessed using a hydrogen bonding model [14]. Thus the relaxation envelope for the wet resin was predicted /Figure 2/.

Figure 3. Comparison of Predicted DMTA Curves for the Base Resins Components to the Data for 924-epoxy Resin Containing 9.3% Residual Moisture

Predictions of Yield Stress and Young Modulus

Since the energy of interaction in the GIM (introduced as the potential, ϕ) is calculated from the van der Waals forces between a single mer unit and six surrounding repeat units, the yield in the model is described as an energy at which the distance, r between these adjacent interactive sites begins to increase [11]. Important engineering parameters such as yield stress can be estimated from equation 5, obtained by expanding GIM potential (equation 1).

$$\sigma_y = 1.35 \cdot B \cdot (1 - \sqrt{\tan \delta_B}) \cdot \frac{N}{E_{coh}} (Tg - T) \quad (5)$$

where B is the bulk modulus (MPa), $\tan \delta_B$ is the loss of tangent through the secondary relaxations.

For many crosslinked thermoset resins failure by tensile fracture occurs before yielding [15]. Therefore the yield stress is often determined in compression. Thus the predictive equation for compressive stress σ_{cy} in GIM is expressed from tensile stress (σ_y) by scaling it with Poisson's ratio.

$$\sigma_{cy} = \sigma_y / 2\nu \quad (6)$$

The bulk modulus in equation 5 is expressed as the strength of interaction energy per volumetric expansion of the polymer.

$$B = 1.5 \cdot \frac{\phi}{V - V_0} \quad (7)$$

where V and V_0 are GIM specific volumes of a chain at the defined set of energy condition and at minimum energy state of a conformation respectively

It is also given in GIM as a function of chain separation distance.

$$B = 1.7 \cdot 10^6 \frac{E_{coh}}{V_w} \frac{\left[2 \left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right)^6 - \left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right)^{12} \right]}{\left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^2 - 1} \quad (8)$$

By using an empirical correlation for the separation distance, equation 8 was further simplified and is written for ambient temperature as:

$$B_{am} = 6.4 \frac{E_{coh}}{V_w} \quad (9)$$

By combining the equations 5, 6 and 9, the yield stress in compression can be written as:

$$\sigma_{cy} = \frac{4.32}{\nu} (1 - \sqrt{\tan \delta_B}) \frac{N}{V_w} (Tg - T) \quad (10)$$

where the number of degrees of freedom N in equations 5 and 10 is taken as that of an average polymer repeat unit:

$$N = N_{mon} - fN_L + X_{stH1}N_{H1} + X_{stH2}N_{H2} \quad (11)$$

The Poisson's ratio in equation 10 is estimated by Seitz formula 12 which is described in detail by Bicerano [16]

$$\nu = 0.513 - 0.03054 \sqrt{\frac{\sum V_w}{\sum L_m}} \quad (12)$$

where V_w is the van der Waals volume and L_m is the length in a fully extended conformation of the resin component. The original equation 12 assumes the van der Waals volume and chain length of a polymer repeat unit. For complex resins it is impossible to parameterize the chain length of an average mer unit on a stoichiometric basis thus the component contribution principle for the length of the segments and van

der Waals volumes was found to be accurate. The length in fully extended conformation for monomer and hardener was determined by the HyperChem modelling software package.

The loss tangent is a function of the Poisson's ratio and is calculated from equation 13 given by formula 14:

$$\nu = 0.5 \cdot [1 - 0.33 \cdot (1 - \sqrt{\tan \delta})^2] \quad (13)$$

$$\tan \delta = \left(\sqrt{\frac{\nu - 0.5}{-0.165}} - 1 \right)^2 \quad (14)$$

The van der Waals volume in equation 10 is that of an average mer unit and is calculated from the stoichiometric coefficient:

$$V_w = V_{w \text{ mon}} + x_{st} \cdot V_{w \text{ H}} \quad (15)$$

where $V_{w \text{ mon}}$ is the van der Waals volume of the monomer, $V_{w \text{ H}}$ - is the van der Waals volume of hardener.

Using the GIM method we modelled the yield stress of three simple epoxy resins for which the experimental values taken for comparison were acquired from the literature /Table 2/ [17-18].

Table 2. Predicted Values of Yield Stress (MPa) Compared to Experimental

Resin Type	Degree of Cure	$\tan \delta_b$	$\sigma_{cy, \text{ calc}}$	$\sigma_{cy, \text{ exp}}$
MY0510-DDS	0.95	0.062	191	203
MY721-DDS	0.87	0.060	186	180
MY721-DDS	0.70	0.060	175	167

The tensile modulus can also be estimated from GIM rules. Such an estimate is given through bulk modulus (equation 9). The crosslink density has a strong influence over the bulk modulus. Therefore to include this into equation 9, a new estimate of cohesive energy is required. The cohesive energy in equation 9 represents the strength of interaction per volume and is written in GIM for a linear molecule. This increases with the degree of crosslinking above the critical level ($C=0.5$) and is calculated as a cohesive energy of a linear chain with an additional increment. The van der Waals volume is assumed to be insignificantly affected by crosslinking and the main model parameter, the cohesive energy, in equation 9 can be obtained from equation 3 by scaling it over the resin Tg.

The estimate of T_g was obtained from equation 3 using the previously described algorithm [12]. The calculated values are given in Tables 3-4.

Table 3. Model Parameters and Glass Transition Temperature for MY721-DDS Systems

Wt %	n_{DDS}	$x_{st\ DDS}$	C	$C_{mon-DDS}$	f_{mon}	$f_{DDS-max}$	ΔE_{ether} J/mol	$T_g, ^\circ C$ calc.
26	0.62	0.46	0.87	0.65	3.79	4	3808	281
			0.7	0.48	3.79			225

Table 4. Model Parameters and Glass Transition Temperature of MY0510-DDS System

Wt %	n_{DDS}	$x_{st\ DDS}$	C	$C_{mon-DDS}$	f_{mon}	$f_{DDS-max}$	ΔE_{ether} J/mol	$T_g, ^\circ C$ calc.
28	0.47	0.34	0.95	0.62	3	4	6440	274

Equation 3 expresses the cohesive energy per number of degrees of freedom of the crosslinked polymer. Since equation 9 is derived for a linear chain, the cohesive energy (including an increment in cohesive energy due to crosslinking) should be rescaled on the basis of the number of degrees of freedom of a linear molecule. The estimate of the number of degrees of freedom for the linear molecule N_{Lin} is obtained from equation 16 and the final estimate from equation 3 by taking the number of degrees of freedom of the linear molecule N_{Lin} .

$$N_{Lin} = N_{mon} - N_L f_{mon} 0.5 \quad (16)$$

where 0.5 is the degree of cure of the linear polymer, N_{mon} and f_{mon} are the number of degrees of freedom and functionality of the monomer.

The tensile moduli of three resins could then be estimated from equation 17, as shown in Table 5.

$$E = 3 \cdot (1 - 2\nu) \cdot B \quad (17)$$

Table 5. Predicted Youngs Moduli of Epoxy Resins as a Function of Degree of Cure.

Resin Type	C	$T_g, ^\circ C$	V_w	E, Gpa
MY0510-DDS	95	273	198	3.70
MY721-DDS	87	281	293	3.42
MY721-DDS	70	225		2.96

DISCUSSION

Group Interaction modelling showed that the estimated glass transition temperatures are in good agreement with experimental data. The modelled relaxation envelope indicates that the shifts of the individual component peaks by moisture can explain the secondary relaxations of a wet resin blend. The thermomechanical behaviour recorded and shown in Figures 1,3 indicate that the formation of a low temperature component in $\tan \delta$, on moisture absorption, can be attributed to differential plasticization of the differing network components. Thus the shoulder which occurs can be assigned to the plasticization of components TGDDM-DICY and MY0510-DDS which overlap /Figure 3/. Plasticization of the MY0510-DICY network appears responsible for the shoulder at 120 °C, which determines the maximum service temperature of the wet resin.

Important mechanical properties of epoxy based matrices such as yield stress and tensile modulus can also be predicted as a function of the degree of cure. Lower crosslink density results in a lower interaction energy per volume and a higher probability of ductile behaviour. Yield stress is highly important in the prediction of stress concentration factors near fibre-breaks in a composite [19].

Future work will involve developing predictive models to assess the effect of moisture on relevant matrix parameters like yield stress and tensile modulus. For more complex systems such as 924-epoxy which contains toughening modifiers the experimental $\tan \delta$ relaxation envelopes for the wet resin may be used to predict failure mechanisms by assuming that a similar trend in linear expansion coefficient can give rise to higher residual thermal strains in a laminate.

CONCLUSION

Predictive results of GIM based models were found to be consistent with experimental data. The method is highly effective for the prediction of glass transition temperatures, the effect of moisture on $\tan \delta$. Estimates of relevant mechanical properties have been made. This opens up the opportunity for incorporating matrix predictions into composite theories.

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